

results the cell might be explored to find out the pK values of MgSO₄ at other temperatures.

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Classical Coulomb Energies $J_L(\rho)$ and $J_{NL}(\rho)$ of an Atomic Charge Distribution. Studies with a Two-parameter Charge Density Function

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THE present work is devoted to estimate the coulomb energies for first row of atoms under local and non-local approximations. In view of this, two-parameter statistical model for atoms suggested by Gazquez and Parr¹ has been used under density function formalism. It is seen that the gradient correction to the kinetic energy is necessary for the estimation of these values.

During the few years there has been a lot of interest in the density functional approach to interpret the chemical and physical properties of atomic and molecular systems in terms of density, and it is highly desirable to use this quantity as a basic variable in quantum chemistry. Yet no theory has been developed to relate electron density directly to other quantities like energy, satisfactorily. For this, some kind of approximation has to be made.

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Some of these lead to the results which are comparable with the Hartree-Fock values in some respect. In many cases they give poor and unphysical results.

Many attempts have been made, using various models, like Thomas-Fermi² model and its extension give considerable insight into the properties of true electronic systems.

The main interest in density-functional description of the electronic structure of an atom is the classical repulsion between electronic charge distribution and itself, given as

$$J(\rho) = 1/2 \iint \frac{\rho(\mathbf{r}_1)\rho(\mathbf{r}_2)}{r_{12}} d\tau_1 d\tau_2 \quad (1)$$

where, ρ is the total electron density for an atom in its ground state. It is also quite interesting to make the approximation to $J(\rho)$ and the equivalent from of equation (1) (already proposed³ and studied⁴ in detail) is the so-called local approximation, given by

$$J_L(\rho) = B_0 N^{2/3} \int \rho^{4/3} d\tau \quad (2)$$

where, B_0 is the universal constant and N the number of electrons.

In the present paper, the form of the density function used is given by

$$\rho(\gamma) = \frac{C}{(A+\gamma)^{2n}} \quad (3)$$

where, C is the normalisation constant, and A and n are variational parameters determined by the minimisation of the total energy. An energy-density functional with gradient correction upto fourth order in kinetic energy is

$$E(\rho) = T_0(\rho) + T_2(\rho) + V_{ne}(\rho) + V_{ee}(\rho) + \frac{K(\rho) + T_4(\rho)}{K(\rho) + T_4(\rho)} \quad (4)$$

where,

$$T_0(\rho) = \left(\frac{3}{10}\right) (3\pi^2)^{2/3} \int \rho^{5/3}(\gamma) d\tau$$

$$T_2(\rho) = \frac{1}{8} \int \frac{(\nabla\rho)^2}{\rho} d\tau$$

$$T_4(\rho) = \frac{(3\pi^2)^{-2/3}}{540}$$

$$\left[\int \left[\rho^{1/3} \left(\frac{\nabla\rho}{\rho}\right)^2 - \frac{9}{8} \left(\frac{\nabla\rho}{\rho}\right) \left(\frac{\nabla\rho}{\rho}\right)^2 + \frac{1}{3} \left(\frac{\nabla\rho}{\rho}\right)^4 \right] d\tau \right]$$

$$V_{ee}(\rho) = 0.4702 \int \rho^{4/3}(\gamma) d\tau$$

$$k(\rho) = \beta_1 Z^{2/3} \int \rho^{4/3}(\gamma) d\tau$$

$$V_{ne}(\rho) = -Z \int \rho(\gamma) d\tau$$

We have used the two-parameter statistical model of Gazquez and Parr to estimate the classical coulomb energies of first row of atoms and the results are reported here. We have used the following three different energy-density functionals for obtaining the two-parameter charge density distributions: model-I: an energy-density functional similar to the Thomas-Fermi density (TFD) model^{5,6} (i.e. Eqn. 4 without $T_2(\rho)$ and $T_4(\rho)$ terms); model-II: simple TFD model with

gradient correction upto second order^{7,8} (i.e. Eqn. 4 without $T_4(\rho)$ term); model-III: TFD model with gradient correction to kinetic energy upto fourth order⁹ (i.e. Eqn. 4). The charge density distribution obtained from the use of the above are used to estimate $J_L(\rho)$ and the results of the study are shown in Table 1. For the first row of atoms,

TABLE 1—CLASSICAL COULOMB ENERGY, $J_L(\rho)$ (ATOMIC UNITS)—LOCAL APPROXIMATION

At. no.	Model			HF*
	I	II	III	
3	4.6	4.0	3.9	4.1
4	8.9	7.8	7.7	7.2
5	14.8	13.3	13.1	11.7
6	22.4	20.4	20.8	17.8
7	31.9	29.8	29.2	26.2
8	43.4	40.2	40.1	36.6
9	56.9	53.0	52.9	50.9
10	72.6	67.9	67.8	66.1

*Ref. 11.

the value of constant B_0 is found to be 0.9058, compared with the values obtained by Bartolotti and Parr¹⁰ being 0.9299. The value obtained by us, for the neutral atoms, is 1.66% (standard percentage error) of the actual or Hartree-Fock values, if the use of Eqn. (3) is made. Furthermore, the results are shown in Table 2 when the addition of the first 'gradient correction' to Eqn. (2) is made, giving the so-called non-local approximation having the formula of the form,

$$J_{NL}(\rho) = BN^{2/3} \int \rho^{4/3} d\tau - CN^{4/3} \int \left(\frac{\nabla \rho}{\rho^{4/3}} \right)^2 d\tau \quad (5)$$

where, B and C are constants having the values 1.8116 and 0.0064 respectively. The justification equation (5) is already discussed¹⁰. By comparing the results of Tables 1 and 2, it is interesting to note that the results improve as one goes from model-I to model-III. In the case of F and Ne atoms model-I seems to be better (Table 2).

TABLE 2—CLASSICAL COULOMB ENERGY, $J_{NL}(\rho)$ (ATOMIC UNITS)—NON-LOCAL APPROXIMATION

At. no.	Model			HF*
	I	II	III	
3	4.2	3.6	3.6	4.1
4	8.0	7.4	7.1	7.2
5	13.4	12.1	12.0	11.7
6	20.8	19.5	18.4	17.8
7	28.9	27.6	26.5	26.2
8	39.4	37.4	36.3	36.6
9	51.6	48.1	48.0	50.9
10	66.8	61.6	61.5	66.1

*Ref. 11.

It appears from the present study that the gradient correction to kinetic energy is quite important for the estimation of $J_L(\rho)$ and $J_{NL}(\rho)$ values. Our next theoretical step is to extend this study to the electron density distribution in an atom-metal interaction.

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Synthesis and Biological Activity of N_1 -Substituted-3-methyl-5-pyrazolones and related Compounds

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PYRAZOLES are found to possess promising antiviral activity¹. Some of the oxopyrazoles exhibit various biological activities². Many pyrazole derivatives possess antiinflammatory activity³. Irikura⁴ reported that 3,5-dimethyl pyrazolones have anti-diabetic property. We have, therefore, synthesised the title compounds and evaluated their biological activity.

The synthesis involved the condensation of substituted-aroxyhydrazines with ethyl acetoacetate in dioxane to give ethyl butarate-2-substituted-aroxyhydrazones (1). **1a-k** on cyclisation in refluxing *o*-dichlorobenzene gave 2-methyl(1-substituted-aroxy)-2-pyrazolin-5-ones (**2a-k**), which with an aryl aldehyde in presence of fused sodium acetate and glacial acetic acid yielded the corresponding mono-arylidene derivatives (**3a-x**) (Scheme 1). Compound **3** decolourised bromine water and showed a broad ir peak at 1695 cm^{-1} indicating the presence of ring ketone. The signal due to olefinic proton at δ 5.8 indicates the condensation of the aldehyde with pyrazolone ring at C_4 -position.

Biological activity: All the compounds were tested for their antibacterial activity using cup-plate agar diffusion technique⁵ against *S. aureus* and *E. coli* at 25 and 50 mg ml^{-1} concentration using chloromycetin as a standard (Tables 1 and 2).